

Otsego Schools Project, Wood County (41.42400, -83.74100)

Since construction in 2021, the Otsego Schools Project’s primary known nutrient benefit has been its runoff prevention due to conversion from an agricultural field and removal as a nutrient source (approximately 0.7 lbs phosphorus per acre each year). The Project’s connection to the watershed is limited, particularly under the dry conditions of 2024, though its soils do have moderate capacity to sorb phosphorus inputs if received. Future sampling to capture hydrologic events will help researchers assess the extent of the floodplain function of the emergent wetland and estimate any resulting nutrient transport reduction. The wetland at this Project has been extensively used for educational purposes.

Surface Water Flow

The hydrology at this Project is passively managed. The Project has 6 acres of restored wetland and consists of a depressional pool complex. There are two emergent wetland pools at the north end that rarely flood, a deep vernal pool in the southwest of the site, and numerous small hummock-hollow pools throughout the southern portion of the site. The site receives water from surface water runoff and typically does not flow out through a defined outflow. The emergent pools receive water from Tontogany Creek when water level rises. A hydrologic event at this Project is defined as a storm event that causes surface water runoff within the site and raises water level in Tontogany Creek to flood-stage.

Nutrient Retention

Converted Farmfield Area	Phosphorus Loss Prevented Annually	
	Per Acre	Total (Mean ± SD)
6 acres	0.7 lbs	11 ± 11 lbs

Enhancement Considerations*

The following practices may yield increased nutrient removal in this or similar isolated wetland Projects or could be accounted for in future site selection:

- Assess parcel footprint for the ability to capture tile drain, stream, or ditch water inputs, in addition to precipitation, in order to optimize nutrient input potential (i.e., connectivity).

*All considerations are based on the best available science at this time, and all recommended items may not be feasible given physical constraints, resource limitations, and broader management goals.